

The Company as *Communio Personarum*: Applying Wojtyla's Notion of Participation in Business' Internal - External Stakeholder Dynamics

Authored by:

Noime Rigen Alberca (corresponding author)
anoimerigem@gmail.com | ibm.noime.r.21@ukwms.ac.id
ORCID: 0009-0003-2668-4279

Tresia Meilani
ibm.tresia.m.21@ukwms.ac.id

Abstract

This paper examines Karol Wojtyla's view of participation and its role in social interdependence. Participation involves active participation in group endeavors and shared responsibility for individual and community welfare, which is important when aligning internal and external stakeholders. The Stakeholder Salience Framework classifies stakeholders by power, legitimacy, and urgency to help organizations prioritize interaction. Consumers, suppliers, governments, local communities, and competitors influence a firm's operations, ethics, and social responsibility. Beyond business, they promote ethical and spiritual values, responsible corporate behavior, fair employee treatment, and environmental conservation. Consumer feedback customizes products and services, while suppliers improve efficiency. CSR and transparency build community support and brand loyalty, with external stakeholders acting as advocates, risk overseers, and reputation boosters. External stakeholders contribute to democratic participation and equitable societal outcomes, supporting deliberative democracy, the social contract, and ethical commitments. Starbucks, GE, and Nestle demonstrate the benefits of external stakeholder engagement in CSR and decision-making. Internal stakeholders including employees, management, and shareholders drive organizational participation. The philosophy of collective welfare emphasizes matching individual aspirations with communal aims. Leadership integrity and morality are essential to workplace engagement through shared ideals, inclusivity, collaboration, and empowerment. Google, Zappos, and Costco involve internal stakeholders in decision-making to improve quality, accountability, and company success. Stakeholder Theory emphasizes the significance of addressing all parties' interests, making internal and external stakeholder connections difficult. Effective communication, ethical guidance, employee engagement, social and environmental responsibility, incentive alignment, stakeholder involvement, crisis management, regulatory compliance, and progress monitoring are needed to align these stakeholders' goals. Leadership and company culture must emphasize transparency and collaboration to foster participation. Governance promotes inclusive decision-making and communication.

I. I. Introduction

In the realm of modern commerce, where the relentless pursuit of profit and competition often take the center stage, many companies have now realized that for the company or organization to be successful and sustainable, it is important to take into consideration that the company is a community and therefore a *communio personarum* (communion of persons). Since it is composed of persons therefore it possesses a communal spirit. This notion, coming from the philosophical musing of Karol Wojtyla (St. John Paul II), transcends the ordinary boundaries of business ethics and challenges the conventional norms of corporate engagement. According to Wojtyla, participation as a moral activity is being-with and acting-for others with the aim of advancing the common good (Wojtyla, 1979). Wojtyla's concept of participation invites us to envision the business entity as a *Communio Personarum*, a living and breathing community of persons bound by a shared destiny.

In this paper we seek to unravel the application of Wojtyla's theory of participation, exploring its ethical and philosophical implications when applied to the intricate tapestry of corporate life. We will look deeper into the very essence of participation, where the individual is not a mere cog in the corporate machinery but a conscious and active contributor to a higher communal purpose.

By looking through the idea of *Commune Personarum*, we shall seek to redefine the concept of corporate social responsibility, reshaping the notion of what businesses can and should be in our society. We will seek to understand the dynamics within and outside the corporate walls, knowing that both the internal and external stakeholders play an important role in fostering a culture of participation. Man's fulfillment is something which requires an active interaction with the world because it is through this interaction that he is called upon to perform specific actions which will inevitably form him as a person (Mejos, 2007). Drawing from the real-world examples and cases, we will try to unveil how businesses have successfully translated these principles into action.

We will also try to tackle the challenges and obstacles that corporations might have to face when applying this notion to their corporate environment. Our compass in this journey is looking at strategies for aligning the interests of the stakeholders, and examining the profound impact that leadership and corporate culture have on realizing the vision of *Commune personarum* in the corporate world.

I. II. Understanding Wojtyla's Notion of participation

Notion of Participation

"A full human life requires material necessities and moral, social, intellectual, and spiritual progress that cannot be achieved in isolation. Social life is necessary for our perfection (Wishloff, 2018)." When we say participation in the common word basis, we mean the act of taking part in something. We can cite an example, for instance, participating in a choir, organization, fraternity groups, etc. In this paper we are not merely focusing on that shallow meaning of participation but rather we will go deeper into the moral activity of participation. Karol Wojtyla' in his work *The Acting Person* in 1975 states that "the expression '*together with others*' lacks the necessary precision and does not sufficiently describe the reality it refers to" (Wojtyla, 1975). Man's existence is intertwined with the presence of other individuals, to the extent that we can assert that he coexists with them. The hallmark of the communal or social feature is fundamentally ingrained in the very

fabric of human existence. Participation is the property of a person as well as an ability to share in the humanity of others (Mejos, 2007). Therefore, the ongoing pursuit of solutions to questions about one's identity and the world is a shared responsibility for both individuals and the community as a whole.

Any ethical theory must begin with a deep understanding of human subjectivity. Action signifies an important point in the expression of an individual. The human person is a unique and unrepeatable individual. Each person has an inherent dignity, freedom, and the capacity for moral action. Thus, human beings are capable of self-knowledge and self-possession. Their intellectual faculties allow them to rise above the level of sensory particulars to achieve conceptual understanding (Wishloff, 2021). Wojtyla also emphasized the centrality of the ethical act, which is conscious, deliberate, and a free choice made by an individual. Human actions therefore are not merely a set of rules to follow, but rather a result of personal choices driven by individuals values, beliefs, and conscience. In his writing *Love and Responsibility*, Wojtyla mentioned that "A person differs from a thing in structure and in degree of perfection. To the structure of the person belongs an 'interior', in which we find the elements of spiritual life, and it is this that compels us to acknowledge the spiritual nature of the human soul, and the peculiar perfectibility of the human person. This determines the value of the person. A person must not be put on the same level as a thing (or for that matter as an individual animal): the person possesses spiritual perfectibility, and is by way of being an (embodied) spirit, not merely a 'body' magnificently endowed with life. Between the psyche of an animal and the spirituality of a man, there is an enormous distance, an uncrossable gulf" (Wojtyla, 1993). Wojtyla characterizes human agency as a conscious and intentional process, referred to as either "man-acts" or "I-act". When an individual participates in an activity, it is a deliberate decision as they possess autonomy over themselves and their behaviors. During this phase, the person undergoes what Wojtyla refers to as the "moment of efficacy," in which they perceive themselves as the source and catalyst of the action. This indicates their acknowledgment of being the primary agents causing events to occur.

Moreover, human activities not only serve as a reflection of an individual's character, but also possess a moral and existential aspect. Each action possesses an inherent quality that can be either positive or negative, contingent upon the nature of the act itself. Put simply, activities possess not just a practical aspect but also a moral and existential importance. Emphasizing the significance of moral principles is crucial, as they not only influence the intrinsic nature of human behaviors but also have a lasting impact on individuals. An individual's moral and existential identity is significantly influenced by their activities, regardless of whether they are good or wicked. Essentially, an individual can be likened to a project, continuously molding their existence through self-directed endeavors. True fulfillment is not solely achieved by accomplishing a task; it is derived from personal growth through engaging in morally decent actions. Only by experiencing both pleasure and satisfaction can an individual genuinely comprehend and value their own worth and the significance of their efforts.

Hence, the starting point which is the experience of man in terms of gaining a deeper insight into the human person is never in isolation or in opposition to others (Wojtyla, 1993). Human experience encompasses interactions with others. Clearly, the person can only grow when he is in community, in participation with others. Within the society, individuals have the capacity to establish connections with others, thereby enhancing their own self-identity. These are relationships in which human beings mutually reveal themselves to one another in their personal human subjectivity and in all that goes to make up this subjectivity.

Individuals who participate in a collective "we" relationship uncover a unique aspect of being and behavior in conjunction with others. This experience does not entail the loss of one's individuality, but rather a redirection of attention, led by the collective welfare. In such connections, individuals not only recognize their mutual presence and collaboration but also perceive a deep sense of unity. In addition to individual viewpoints, the community of individuals involved in the "we" interaction forms its own shared subjectivity. The establishment of this link is not a result of chance; rather, it arises from deliberate efforts made by individuals who acknowledge that they are not alone in their quest for satisfaction. It arises from a collective comprehension of the universal human nature that binds all individuals together. Engaging in a collective partnership not only allows individuals to form a distinct bond with others but also enhances their comprehension of both their own human nature and the human nature of their peers.

When a human engages in authentic actions, they are always expressing their personal identity and the ability to make a free choice. Thus, the act itself, as long as it is initiated by an individual, has significance in the personal level even before considering its moral implications. The personalistic value of the action lies in the fact that the action is performed and in it the person realizes himself according to the structure which is proper to him (Buttinglione, 1997). An individual's existence and conduct are influenced by their interactions with others. Wojtyla employs the concept of "Participation" to elucidate how an individual, in the context of collective endeavors, maintains the personal significance of their own activities while simultaneously making active contributions towards the achievement of common actions and their outcomes. Participation can be understood in two different ways: it signifies a characteristic of the individual, demonstrated by their ability to incorporate their unique essence into their presence and activities while coexisting and cooperating with others. Additionally, it represents the ability to establish a connection with the collective human experience of others. Participation basically serves to express the property by virtue of which we as persons exist and act together with others, while not ceasing to be ourselves or to fulfill ourselves in action, in our own acts. The ability to exist and act together with others in such a way that in this existing and acting we remain ourselves and actualize ourselves, which means our own (Wojtyla). Participation is a beneficial connection between individuals as it enables them to perceive their own existence and engage in collective actions with others.

Participation enables both self-realization and communal realization. The capacity for participation indicates an individual's ability to engage in interpersonal relationships with others while also finding fulfillment via their acts. Participation serves as the opposite of alienation, enabling individuals to completely engage with their own identity and also to connect with the shared humanity of others. Participation indicates that humans have a natural inclination towards self-actualization and achieve this by existing and collaborating with others. Thus, the collective welfare and the personal welfare converge inside the individual, who actively pursues them in collaboration with others. Participation entails more than mere physical presence in a collective endeavor. It is conceivable that individuals can coexist as a collective while simultaneously pursuing their objectives independently or in seclusion. Participation signifies an individual's acknowledgement and support of the collective welfare. It is not a spontaneous occurrence, but rather a consequence of an individual's deliberate pursuit of satisfaction and the recognition that they cannot achieve it independently, but must actively seek it in collaboration with others. When participating, an individual desires not just their own well-being but also the well-being of individuals in their vicinity. It enables him to be vulnerable with others and also enables others to express their shared human experience with him. Participation, in essence, enables individuals to enhance their humanity.

Ethical implications of participation in business

Participation is an inherent aspect of the human experience and is deeply integrated into the essence of human beings. Participation transcends beyond mere involvement but rather it is the fundamental nature of our collective human experience. In this context, we examine the significant ethical implications of the notion of participation in the realm of business. Wojtyła's notion of participation will be our basis as we navigate the complex interconnections of human behavior, ethical obligations, and society, providing valuable insights that can revolutionize our approach to business.

The essence of participation is rooted in recognizing and valuing the distinctiveness of every person, their intrinsic worth, and their ability to make ethical choices. Given the distinctiveness of human dignity, it is therefore that all our human actions must be "in conformity with the dignity and integral vocation of the human person" (Wojtyła, 1993). In the realm of commerce, this surpasses the sole objective of generating profits. According to Wishloff Jim, even if profitability is a necessary condition of the firm, it is not a sufficient one. The justification for enterprise is the correspondence of its economic activity with God's plan for man. The practice of management must be an act of love (Wishloff, 2009). Therefore, business leaders and organizations are required to uphold the dignity of all employees, customers, and all internal or external stakeholders. Showing profound respect for every individual and acknowledging their inherent value is not just a moral obligation but also a fundamental responsibility of humanity.

Moreover, participation is not a passive act, it demands active and purposeful involvement from and with individuals. Since participation is necessarily conscious, deliberate, and free choices, this means that it is necessary for individuals to be fully cognizant of their activities, making decisions with intention, and having the freedom to select how they involve themselves. In the context of business, the notion of participation assumes a notable aspect. With that being said, in the realm of business, this call for conscious and deliberate decision-making sets a high standard for ethical conduct. The decision-making process therefore, is not solely prioritizing immediate financial benefits, but rather prioritizing decisions that are ethical and in accordance with the set of moral principles and actions, taking into account the common good. Business leaders, executives, together with all levels of employees of an organization, are expected to make decisions that take into account the wider repercussions on society and the community.

"The 'personalistic' value of the human action -that is, the personal value- is a special and probably the most fundamental manifestation of the worth of the person himself" (Wojtyła, 1979). Human actions have significant moral and ontological importance rather than being superficial or meaningless motions. This poignant revelation shows significant implications for the business arena, urging us to acknowledge our ethical responsibility for the consequences of our activities. In business context, this means that profit alone should not be the exclusive driving principle of business endeavors; we must rather give equal and balanced consideration to the ethical ramifications of our choices and decisions. A responsible enterprise's defining characteristics is not only its financial prosperity, but more importantly, a steadfast commitment to engaging in ethically upright behaviors that provide advantages to both the company and the wider community. In his work, *Fides et Ratio*, Karol Wojtyła (Pope John Paul II) mentioned, if business is to be an agent of authentic human development then, it must respect or honor this teleological reality by what it produces and the production processes it uses to bring these products about. Economic production should not deflect people from achieving their proper human end of sharing the divine life but should assist in the process of sanctification (Wojtyła, 1998). Within this paradigm,

businesses therefore, transcends from mere transactions and profitability to serving as a platform for ethical behavior and cultivating a more virtuous and conscientious corporate culture.

Earlier we have known that the essence of our being is inherently interconnected with a profound sense of communal belonging. Hence, this underlines the intrinsic importance of working together most especially in the corporate realm. It is therefore a strong urge that we acknowledge the immense importance of collaboration and cooperation among all participants in the ecosystem of business; internal and external stakeholders. Cultivating a spirit of unity and a shared purpose is not just a moral ideal; it serves as a crucial element in constructing a more ethical; and prosperous business environment. This unity goes beyond ordinary collaboration; it entails fostering a collective awareness in which each individual, department, and external partner synchronize their endeavors with a common vision. In this harmonious collaboration, businesses discover not only ethical fulfillment but also a long lasting achievement where profitability of the enterprise and the well-being of society are interconnected.

In 1979, Wojtyla mentioned, “The relation of the many ‘I’s’ to the common good seems to be the very core of the social community. Thanks to this relation, people who experience their personal subjectivity, and therefore the actual plurality of human ‘I’s,’ realize that they are a definite ‘we’ and experience themselves in this new dimension. Although the person remains herself, this is a social dimension. It differs from that of the ‘I-you,’ for the direction of the dimension is changed and is indicated by the common good. In this relation the ‘I’ and the ‘you’ find their reciprocal reference in a new dimension: they discover their ‘I-you’ through the common good which constitutes a new unity among them (Wojtyla, 1979). We can deduce that the notion of “we” relationship and the collective subjectivity compels business to transcend individual interests. Business ethics goes beyond simple corporate responsibility; it is about fostering a collective sense of humanity. The notion of participation teaches us that genuine satisfaction stems from individual development through morally upright behaviors. In business, this speaks to the need for both personal and collective fulfillment. Employees ought not to only function as components in a mechanism, but rather should strive to discover significance and intention in their professional endeavors. Businesses ought to actively contribute to the welfare of society, acknowledging that true satisfaction arises from benefiting not only oneself but also the broader community.

Participation compels individuals to engage with the collective human experience of others, thus fostering inclusivity and empathy is also important in the realm of business. Ethical enterprises surpass mere adherence to diversity mandates; they actively foster diversity and inclusion, demonstrating true empathy for the needs and experiences of every person. They acknowledge that human beings' shared humanity is a tapestry of diverse stories and backgrounds. Precisely, individuals coexist and collaborate in their pursuit of fulfillment, hence, reciprocal advantage and mutual benefit is important. Ethical business, strive to provide equal benefit for all stakeholders; internal and external stakeholders, while avoiding exploitative or unbalanced agreements. Collaboration therefore, is not merely a trendy term but a fundamental basis of an ethical company culture.

Respectively, the substantial ethical implications of participation in business extend beyond mere philosophical contemplation; they serve as a guide towards a more conscientious and sustainable approach to commerce. Participation compels enterprises to uphold human dignity, make ethical choices, assume moral accountability, cultivate a sense of community, appreciate shared perspectives, pursue the sense of community, promote inclusivity and empathy, and

emphasize coexistence and collaboration. These principles serve as a guide toward a more ethical and humane business environment.

I. III. *Communio Personarum* in Business

The “Company as ‘*Communio Personarum*’”

In contemporary society, the “company” or enterprises is typically associated with corporate entities, profit margins, financial returns, and market capitalization. However, when looking at what the company is made of, -people as internal and external stakeholders-, and considering the dignity of the stakeholders that comprises the company, we can therefore say that the “company as *communio personarum*”. This notion therefore, prompts us to regard corporations as entities that transcend their purely economic function. Instead, it invites us to perceive the complex systems of human beings bounded by shared values, objectives, and responsibilities, creating a community of individuals. Hence, this concept challenges us to reconsider our ethical position on businesses and raises fundamental questions regarding moral dimensions of corporate existence.

The *communio personarum* means “living in a reciprocal 'for,' in a relationship of reciprocal gift. ... In fact, the gift reveals, so to speak, a personal characteristic of personal existence, or even of the very essence of the person [which is realized] only by existing 'with someone' — and put even more deeply and completely, by existing 'for someone.' (John Paul II, 1979). The idea of communitarianism also got a special attention in the 1800's by the British Chartist Goodwyn Barmby. He started communitarianism as a philosophy “that emphasizes the connection between the individual and the community. Although the community might be a family unit, communitarianism usually is understood, in the wider, philosophical sense, as a collection of interactions, among a community of people in a given place (geographical location), or among a community who share an interest or who share a history. Communitarian philosophy is based upon the belief that a person’s social identity and personality are largely molded by community relationships with a smaller degree of development being placed on individualism.” Combining these two concepts, *communio personarum* therefore, denotes a community of individuals. Hence, the company means that the corporation is not merely a profit-oriented entity devoid of emotions, soulless; it is rather a collective of individuals with dignity, unique experiences, beliefs and values.

The company as *communio personarum*, therefore requires moral duty and accountability. Since, corporation is a communion of persons, it is then evident that each person within the organization bears both the duty and responsibility for moral accountability for its actions. This notion opposes the conventional division between human and corporate accountability, urging us to reconsider how we evaluate the ethical actions of companies and the people who comprise them; -internal and external stakeholders.

The ethical and social responsibility of companies

In today's business discourse, the importance of social and ethical responsibility in relation to corporate governance and sustainability is paramount. This relates to a thorough understanding of the ethical and social responsibilities that businesses have toward their various stakeholders, which include local communities, workers, clients, and the environment. The current study has a strong theoretical foundation that provides an organized framework for analyzing and evaluating a company's social and ethical behavior.

Ethical Analysis in the perspective of “Normative Ethics”

Normative ethics, which is based on philosophy, focusses on “justifying why a particular ethical standard might apply to a given practice and articulating the reasons for upholding such an ideal”(Laczniaak and Murphy, 2019, p. 401). It provides framework and normative guidelines for human behavior, helping individuals, society, businesses, and any other entity to make ethical decisions and resolve moral dilemmas. Normative ethics comprises a range of moral theories that present distinct methods for identifying actions that are ethically correct. The positive ethics focus on how individuals make ethical choices instead of how they should make them. (Tjandra, N. C., Aroean, L., & Prabandari, Y. S., 2020). There are three major categories of moral theories: deontological, consequentialism, and virtue ethics.

Deontological ethics often associated with philosophers like Immanuel Kant, posits that actions are intrinsically right or wrong, regardless of their consequences. The significance of moral laws and obligations is emphasized, such as the categorical imperative, which says that people should only act in ways that they would want to become generally accepted norms. According to deontological ethics, actions have associated moral value. This implies that some behaviors are regarded as intrinsically good or bad, independent of the results they yield. Simply, an action's morality is inherent in its nature and is not dependent on how it turns out. Deontological ethics emphasizes moral laws and obligations. These guidelines offer direction for figuring out what behaviors are ethically required, acceptable, and unacceptable.

Similar to utilitarianism, consequentialist theories view that normative properties depend only on consequences. Utilitarianism holds that a deed is ethically justified if it results in the greatest amount of overall happiness or utility for the largest number of people. These theories are based on the idea that an action's moral worth is primarily and often exclusively determined by its outcomes. According to this theory, the basic tenet for judging an action's morality is the principle of utility, which holds that a deed is morally justified if it maximizes overall happiness or utility for the largest number of people.

Philosophers such as Aristotle established virtue ethics, which emphasizes an individual's character over specific acts or outcomes. It places a strong emphasis on developing virtues like bravery, honesty, and compassion as the foundation for moral conduct. It may, initially, be identified as the one that emphasizes the virtues, or moral character, in contrast to the approach that emphasizes duties or rules (deontology) or that emphasizes the consequences of actions (consequentialism). Virtues are admirable attributes or qualities of character that are thought to be necessary for leading a morally upright life. Examples of these include honesty, courage, compassion, and integrity. It is acknowledged by virtue ethics that virtues ought to be moderated and balanced. For example, bravery is a virtue, but cowardice is a deficiency and recklessness is an excess of courage. Finding the ideal balance between virtues and vices is encouraged by virtue ethics.

Businesses must adopt normative ethical frameworks in the corporate setting in order to direct their decision-making. Their understanding of moral obligations and adherence to ethical standards, regardless of financial consequences, is aided by deontological ethics. In line with corporate social responsibility, consequentialism emphasizes the significance of taking into account wider effects on stakeholders, society, and the environment. Corporate cultures that value moral qualities like honesty and integrity among leaders and employees are fostered by virtue ethics. Essentially, normative ethics provides vital direction for companies that aim to uphold moral standards in their operations and dealings with stakeholders and to make moral decisions.

Social Responsibility Analysis

Social Responsibility theory, an offshoot of Libertarian philosophy evolved following widespread virulent criticisms that trailed the Libertarian Theory (Obagwu, P. U., & Idris, K. M., 2019). Libertarianism is a political and ethical theory that emphasizes individual liberty and limited government involvement in social and economic issues. Libertarians take individual freedom as the paramount political value and understand coercion to be the antithesis of that freedom. It states that everyone has the freedom to live their lives as they see fit, to make their own decisions, and to keep the things they have worked hard for. Libertarianism frequently advocates a free-market, laissez-faire approach in business and economics, wherein government regulation is minimized and voluntary exchanges are encouraged. Although libertarianism has its supporters, it has also come under fire, especially when it comes to issues like worker rights, income inequality, environmental protection, and access to healthcare and education. Opponents contend that a strictly libertarian approach can have unfavorable effects because it occasionally puts individual liberty ahead of the welfare of the community.

The "Social Responsibility theory" is an attempt to address these libertarian critiques. While acknowledging the value of individual liberties, it contends that companies and people alike must also take society's welfare into account. Stated differently, this implies that companies ought to consider their effects on the environment, workers, and customers, in addition to their own financial interests and personal gains. The goal of the social responsibility theory is to strike a balance between societal responsibility and personal freedom. It pushes companies and people to behave morally and to think about how their actions will affect society and the environment. This could entail activities like philanthropy, fair labor standards, environmental sustainability, and corporate social responsibility.

Social responsibility has gained traction and credibility; it is now recognized that people, planet, and profit are mutually inclusive. Just as quality leads to profit, responsibility leads to sustainable profit. The theory of Social Responsibility in business suggests that companies ought to consider their obligations to workers, customers, the environment, and the local community in addition to maximizing profits for their shareholders. This can take many different forms, such as sustainable development projects, charitable endeavors, and fair labor standards. The rise of the Social Responsibility theory is indicative of how philosophical and ethical theories are changing as societies deal with difficult moral issues pertaining to commerce, the economy, and social welfare. It is a reflection of a conversation that is still going on about how people and businesses can help create a society that is more just and equal.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a concept that has gained significant importance in the business world in recent decades. CSR refers to a company's commitment to operating in an ethical and responsible manner by considering the social and environmental impact of their actions in achieving economic goals. CSR refers to the responsibility that companies assume for all their stakeholders, who may be investors or any other individuals or groups that have stakes in companies (Furlotti, K., & Mazza, T., 2022). A company's commitment to addressing the ethical, social, and environmental impacts of its operations is outlined in the CSR framework. It entails taking a proactive stance when conducting business in a way that benefits stakeholders as a whole in addition to shareholders. Businesses are expected to understand and carry out their obligations to different stakeholders.

Businesses are expected to understand and carry out their obligations to different stakeholders. People or organizations with an interest, or a "stake," in the success and operations

of the company are known as stakeholders. A difficult task of CSR is striking a balance between the needs and interests of these different stakeholders. Businesses want to create a win-win scenario in which they benefit the environment and community at large while simultaneously generating profits for their shareholders. In order to manage the intricate network of obligations to these parties, companies frequently utilize Carroll's CSR Pyramid.

Carroll's CSR Pyramid, which outlines four levels of responsibility, is frequently used to conceptualize CSR. This model gives the structure organizations need to meet the economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic demands of Business. These tiers consist of economic responsibility (generating profits), legal responsibility (observing rules and laws), ethical responsibilities (acting morally and justly), and philanthropic responsibility (generating benefits to the community on a voluntary basis). The CSR Pyramid's base layer tackles an organization's financial obligations. For economic responsibility, this implies that making money and maintaining a company's financial stability are a business's main goals. Profits are necessary both to reward investors/owners and also for business growth when profits are reinvested back into the business (Carroll A.B., 2016). Being financially viable is a company's primary goal since it enables it to endure, expand, and give returns to investors. A business would find it difficult to carry out its other obligations in the absence of financial success. The legal responsibilities layer deals with a company's need to follow local, national, and international laws, rules, and regulations established by government authorities. Businesses are expected and required to comply with these laws and regulations as a condition of operating (Carroll A.B., 2016). Respecting the law is necessary to keep the peace, safeguard consumers, and guarantee fair competition. Society expects businesses to operate and conduct their affairs in an ethical fashion (Carroll A.B., 2016). It also aids in leveling the playing field for companies. Beyond the letter of the law, ethical responsibilities include conducting business with justice, integrity, and consideration for stakeholders' welfare. Moral precepts serve as the foundation for these obligations. In the business world, acting ethically enhances reputation, trust, and goodwill among stakeholders. It aims to do what is morally correct and goes above and beyond what is required by law. Corporate philanthropy includes all forms of business giving. Corporate philanthropy embraces business's voluntary or discretionary activities (Carroll A.B., 2016). Philanthropic responsibilities, which include voluntary contributions to the community and society above and beyond what is required by law and morality, are represented by the top layer of the CSR Pyramid. Although they are not required, philanthropic duties are considered as a means for businesses to give back and improve society. These deeds can improve a business's standing and advance social welfare.

In summary, corporate social responsibility, or CSR, has become a key idea in the contemporary business environment, representing a moral and responsible way of doing business. It denotes a business's dedication to taking into account how its actions will affect society and the environment in addition to its financial objectives. Understanding that companies have a variety of stakeholders to answer to, such as investors, staff, clients, communities, and the environment, is fundamental to corporate social responsibility (CSR). CSR is a broad term that recognizes a business's social responsibility and is supported by the ideas of profit, adherence to the law, moral conduct, and charitable giving on a voluntary basis. Businesses can strike a balance between their financial success and the wider welfare of their stakeholders by upholding these obligations, which will ultimately help to create a more moral and sustainable business environment. In order to manage the intricate network of obligations to these parties, companies frequently utilize Carroll's CSR Pyramid. This framework provides an organized method for carrying out your financial, legal, moral, and charitable obligations.

I. IV. Internal Stakeholder Dynamics

Overview of internal stakeholders (employee, management, shareholders)

According to Nilson (2006: p170), internal stakeholders are those in the management, marketing experts, designers, purchasing, manufacturing, assembly and sales. Internal stakeholders are individuals or groups within a company or organization which has a direct interest in the operations activities, the success of the company, and also the decision making process. There are three primary categories in the internal stakeholders which are the employees, management, and shareholders. These three groups are playing a crucial role in the function and the success of the company to achieve their economic goals.

Employees are the foundation of any company. Company employees are key stakeholders because they create the goods and services issued by a company, and the quality of their work has a direct impact on customer support. They are the people who carry out the regular duties and make a positive impact on the success and productivity of the business. Employees care about job satisfaction, which is influenced by things like a comfortable and secure work environment, fair compensation, and chances for both professional and personal development. Employees worry about striking a balance between their personal and professional lives, and companies that encourage this balance typically have happier and more productive workers. Employees want a clear career path, opportunities for skill development, and advancement within the company. The most important things are equal treatment, equal opportunities, and a workplace without discrimination. Employees appreciate management that communicates with them in an honest and open manner. Motivated and engaged employees are more likely to be dedicated to the company and productive. Employers frequently use employee engagement initiatives to promote a happy workplace.

Most in management are in charge of organizing, planning, and supervising the day-to-day activities of the company. Middle managers, department heads, and executives make up this group. The management is committed to the organization's prosperity and the accomplishment of its strategic objectives. For management, running operations effectively and efficiently is paramount. Their interest is in the no risk of downsizing, good working conditions, decent wages, and bonuses for good work in their departments. Their main objectives are process optimization and resource allocation. One of the most important things in the organization is to identify and develop leadership potential. For the organization to achieve its strategic goals and maintain alignment with all stakeholders, communication within the organization is essential. The organizational culture is often shaped by management, and this has an effect on worker morale and output. The strategic decisions that steer the company's direction are made by management. The interests of shareholders, employees, and other stakeholders must be balanced.

Shareholders are individuals or entities who own shares in the company. Individuals or organizations that own equity or shares in the company are known as shareholders, including institutional investors. They stand to gain financially from the success of the business. The principal concern of shareholders is to obtain a return on their investment. This covers total profitability, capital growth, and dividends. Effective corporate governance procedures are important to shareholders because they guarantee that management acts in their best interests. Access to pertinent company information and financial reporting transparency are priorities for shareholders. How the company controls risk and maintains long-term financial performance is of concern to shareholders. Typically, the way that shareholders exert their influence over a company is by voting on important decisions like major corporate actions and board of directors elections.

In summary, an organization's capacity to successfully manage and strike a balance between the interests of its internal stakeholders determines both its success and sustainability. These internal stakeholders include shareholders, management, and staff members, each of whom is vital to the business's operations and achievement of its financial objectives. An organization's ability to succeed in the long run depends on its ability to balance the interests of these internal stakeholders. The company's overall goals and objectives are supported by a harmonious and productive work environment that is facilitated by ethical decision-making, effective communication, and interest alignment. Furthermore, to promote the success of the company, internal stakeholders frequently collaborate with external stakeholders like suppliers, customers, and government agencies.

The role of internal stakeholders in fostering participation

The notion of participation occupies a pivotal role in the business realm. It serves as a link between individual self-governance and corporate governance demonstrating the reliance of individuals within a community. In Aguas writing *n Person, Action, and Love*, he made a thesis according to Wojtyła's theory of participation saying that in the life of the human person, from his beginning and through his long development, his whole existence is immersed in the two dimensions of the community, -the interpersonal which is the one-to-one interpersonal relationship which is signified by the I-You Relation; and the social dimension which is communal and signified by we relation. There is therefore a need for a human person to participate in attaining his fulfillment as a person. This is equally true in all circumstances in human life, dealing with his family, the closest person he has collaboration with, his neighbors, his friends, and even his place of work. The welfare of an individual as a citizen or a participant in a community aligns with the collective welfare of human society in which they reside. This collective welfare is defined as the societal structure that enables each person to approach their own personal fulfillment to the greatest extent feasible.

Internal stakeholders such as employees, management, and stockholders often have a vested interest in the well-being of the organization, in business we coined this into the term "Agency problem" which is a conflict of interest inherent in any relationship where one party is expected to act in another's best interest. The Theory of participation tells us that the welfare of an individual has to be aligned with the collective welfare of the community, in this case the company. Internal stakeholders' interests therefore, are closely aligned with the success and well-being of the organization. Moreover, given that the common good does not conflict with individuals' well-being within the social framework, internal stakeholders participation should ideally be in harmony with the overall objectives and well-being of the organization/company. When internal stakeholders are given the opportunity to actively participate in the decision making of the company or contribute for the betterment of the group, this can lead to a win-win situation where both individual and the collective interest are served. "Virtue is not achieved in isolation, but through participation in the ordered social whole. Far from there being an inherent incompatibility between the individual and the society, they can be seen to be complementary — i.e., they exist for one another" (Wishloff, 2009). Organizations, moreover, have the structures and systems in place that impact the opportunities for individual development and prosperity. Internal stakeholders play a role in shaping, influencing, or benefitting from these structures.

The internal stakeholders of the company, i.e. managers, employees, and executives play a pivotal role in fostering participation within the organization. They all have roles to play for the common good. There are several dimensions in which we can point out on how internal stakeholders play these roles. First, internal stakeholders, particularly senior management, set the

tone for the company. By promoting shared values, like for instance ethical behavior, transparency, and fairness, they create an environment where participation is encouraged. This value will be the ethical compass guiding individual and collective actions. Participation thrives when individuals feel included and valued. Therefore, it is important that internal stakeholders work together to create an inclusive culture that respects diverse perspectives. This inclusivity ensures that all employees have the voice and can contribute to the collective decision-making process. This collaboration is found at the heart of participation. Thus, it is a must for internal stakeholders to actively foster a collaborative atmosphere where teamwork and cooperation are not simply encouraged but rather rewarded. Men ought to be given meaningful work that utilizes and develops their higher faculties. Responsibility for managing the enterprise would then be broadly diffused. Employees would rightly be seen as associates or partners in the venture (Wishloff, 2018). If employees are empowered, then they are willing to participate. Employee empowerment can be done by delegating responsibility, providing opportunities for skill development, and granting them a say in decision-making process. This enhances the quality of decisions and also reinforces the sense of coexistence and shared responsibility. By “participation” we understand that which corresponds to the transcendence of the person in the act when this act is performed “together with others,” in various social or inter-human relations (Wojtyla, 1969). Furthermore, the role of internal stakeholders extends to ethical leadership. Leaders, apart from setting ethical standards, they should also lead by example. Our words need to convey an impassioned and unflinching witness to life which is "made flesh" in how we provide health care. Our language needs to bear witness to the uniqueness and inestimable worth of every person. Our voices need to bear witness to human dignity for those who have no voice and for those whose voice has been silenced. In the very act of providing health care, we bear witness to human dignity and the gift of life in all its stages of growth and development. Wojtyla's theory of participation therefore encourages leaders to conduct themselves and guide their teams.

Numerous firms actively engage in the practise of involving internal stakeholders, such as employees, in decision-making processes, acknowledging the importance of their engagement. For instance, Google fosters employee engagement by organizing "TGIF" (Thank God It's Friday) meetings, during which employees get the opportunity to interact with corporate leadership and pose inquiries. In its TGIF (Thank God it's Friday) meetings, the upper management also shares private information about company events over the week. Google expects its employees to use this information wisely; thus creating a sense of ownership and transparency among its employees. The company offers a range of employee resource groups that facilitate conversations about diversity, equity, and inclusion among staff members. Another example is that of Zappos. Zappos is renowned for its distinctive approach to corporate culture, characterized by a significant degree of employee involvement in the decision-making process. The organization follows a "holacracy" framework, which grants employees the authority to make decisions within their designated responsibilities. In late 2013, Zappos implemented a unique corporate culture called “holacracy” by replacing its conventional organizational structure. Holacracy is a system that removes traditional managerial hierarchies allowing employees to self-organize to complete work in a way that increases productivity, fosters innovation and empowers anyone in the company with the ability to make decisions that push the company forward. It promotes distributed accountability, authority, and leadership, in the absence of direction from others. This one-way holacracy empowers you to control your work and achieve your goals. Even Costco also implements participation. Costco is renowned for its exemplary treatment of employees and actively solicits their advice on a range of issues. The company's ethos of prioritizing employee well-being and guaranteeing equitable remuneration demonstrates a dedication to engaging internal stakeholders.

I. V. External Stakeholders Dynamics

External stakeholders are the users/customers, distributors, governments, suppliers, communities, laws and regulations (Karim, et al., 2007, pp.8). External stakeholders are

individuals, groups, or entities outside the company or organization that have interest in the company activities, performance, and the outcomes of the company. These stakeholders can significantly influence the organization. Having deep understanding and managing strong relationships with the external stakeholders is essential for the reputation and also the success of the organization. There are several types of external stakeholders which are the customers, suppliers, government and regulatory bodies, local communities, and competitors.

Naturally, customers are the lifeblood of any company. Their purchase of a company's goods or services is how they interact with it, so their role is crucial. By doing this, consumers give the company the vital income it needs to continue operating, grow, and maintain its overall success. In other words, a business cannot grow or survive if it does not have customers. There are five types of customers, loyal customers, impulse customers, discount customers, need-based customers, and wandering customers. Loyal customers are a subset of a company's customer base who are known for their unwavering commitment to the brand and products. They frequently return to the company to make purchases. Impulsive customers are people who decide what to buy on the impulse of the moment and without having a specific item in mind. When they find a good offer or opportunity, they purchase goods. Discount customers are people who shop a lot but mostly rely on sales, markdowns, or discounts to make their purchases. Need-based customers are those who go into a store or browse the internet knowing exactly what they want to buy. Wandering customers may investigate different options or products without having a clear objective in mind because they are unsure of what they want to buy. Consumers expect high-quality goods and services that live up to their expectations. Consumers look for value in the cost they incur. It is crucial to provide quick and efficient customer service, including problem solving. Concerns regarding the company's environmental and ethical policies may exist among customers. While unhappy customers can damage a company's reputation, satisfied customers can become devoted, repeat customers and brand ambassadors.

Suppliers are individuals or companies/businesses that provide products or services to other entities. Suppliers offer the components, raw materials, or services required for a business to function. Suppliers anticipate reliable and timely payment. Developing enduring connections with suppliers can result in more favorable conditions and dependability. Suppliers prefer to collaborate with businesses that follow morally and fairly. Reliable supply chains, cost savings, and access to cutting-edge goods and services can all result from having positive relationships with suppliers. There are two types of suppliers, supplier of product in the form of goods and product supplier in the form of services. Suppliers of goods are organizations or companies that focus on producing, supplying, or marketing tangible goods. These goods can be anything from components and raw materials to completed goods that are prepared for retail sales. Goods suppliers are essential to the supply chain because they guarantee that companies can produce goods or satisfy customer demands by providing the physical products they need. In industries where components or raw materials are converted into finished goods, they are indispensable. On the other hand, Service suppliers are organizations or people who provide consumers or businesses with expertise, assistance, or intangible services. These services can include a broad range of products and services, such as expert advice and consulting as well as maintenance and repair services. Service providers are essential to companies looking for specific knowledge, skills, or support to enhance operations or deal with particular issues. They provide solutions that internal resources might not be able to provide.

A regulatory body, also known as a regulatory authority or just a regulator, is a public organization or government agency that establishes and strengthens legal standards in different

sectors of the economy and public life, such as education, transportation, and workplace health. Organizations are legally obligated to abide by rules, standards, and policies, which are established and enforced by government agencies and regulatory bodies. They are essential to preserving compliance, equity, and order in many different economic sectors. Assuring that organizations follow the law is the main priority of regulatory authorities. To keep the playing field level, safeguard the interests of different stakeholders, and stop non-compliant businesses from gaining an unfair advantage, compliance is essential. Additionally, it protects the welfare and rights of workers and customers. Regulatory agencies are dedicated to protecting the public interest by formulating and implementing laws that tackle matters such as workplace safety, environmental contamination, and ethical business conduct. They try to make sure that companies don't hurt the environment or the general public while also making a positive contribution to society.

Local community is a group of interacting people sharing an environment (Karmaoui, A., Ben Salem, A., & Anees, M. T., 2021). Local communities are important in the context of organizations, particularly those that function in a particular region. Businesses and local communities interactions can have a significant effect on both sides. Organizations are frequently regarded as sources of employment opportunities in local communities. They anticipate that these companies will give locals jobs, which will improve the region's economic health. For nearby communities, the creation of jobs is essential. In addition to improving people's quality of life, it also helps the community's economy grow, lowers unemployment, and might even draw and keep newcomers. Concerns regarding how an organization's operations may affect the environment may exist in a community. They want to know how a company's operations impact the surrounding ecology, the quality of the air and water, and the sustainability of the environment as a whole. Taking care of environmental issues is crucial to keeping good relations with the community. Companies that practice sustainability and environmental responsibility are more likely to win over the community's supporters and steer clear of trouble from residents who respect a clean and healthy environment. It is common for organizations to be expected to support and actively engage with their local community. This involvement can come in the shape of volunteer programs, social responsibility initiatives, charitable endeavors, or alliances with nearby organizations. Relevance: Participating in the community deepens the relationship between the organization and the community and promotes a sense of social responsibility. It shows a dedication to being a responsible corporate citizen and can result in trust, local support, and a favorable public perception.

Competitors are other businesses who can offer the same or similar goods and services to your customers. Competitors are other companies or groups that are involved in the same market or industry as the organization. They are essential in determining how businesses operate and how the competitive environment is shaped. Competitors have a strong desire to comprehend the characteristics of the market in which they compete. This covers elements like the size of the market, room for expansion, customer preferences, and new trends. Competitors must understand market dynamics in order to make well-informed strategic decisions. It helps them to spot market trends, predict shifts in customer needs, and properly position their goods and services. Competitors anticipate an even playing field where all players follow the rules of fair play. This requires complying by antitrust laws and moral business conduct. Businesses compete on the basis of their merits rather than by using unfair advantages when there is fair competition. It prevents monopolistic behavior, fosters efficiency and innovation, and supports a positive business climate.

External stakeholders have a significant impact on how an organization operates, performs, and produces results overall. These stakeholders include users/customers, distributors,

governments, suppliers, communities, and laws and regulations. The organization's success and reputation depend on its ability to comprehend these stakeholders and maintain strong relationships with them. The performance and operations of an organization are greatly impacted by external stakeholders. For a business to succeed and keep a good reputation, it is essential to comprehend and manage relationships with suppliers, customers, authorities, local communities, and rivals. The success of an organization in the long run can be influenced by how responsibly it handles the interests and worries of these external stakeholders.

The role of external stakeholders in promoting participation

A person differs from a thing in structure and in degree of perfection. To the structure of the person belongs an 'interior', in which we find the elements of spiritual life, and it is this that compels us to acknowledge the spiritual nature of the human soul, and the peculiar perfectibility of the human person (Wojtyla, 1993). This therefore, defines the worth of the person. A person should not be equated with an object or even an animal because a person has the potential for spiritual growth and is essentially a spirit inhabiting a body, not just a body with the gift of life. The gap between the mind of an animal and the spirituality of a human is vast and cannot be bridged. Hence, the concept of corporate participation goes beyond the realm of mere business, it extends into the ethical and spiritual dimensions of human existence precisely because "economic production ought to serve this end. Spiritual and moral goods should not be sacrificed to material interests. The want-structure encouraged by enterprise should serve good moral formation. Just because something can be made and sold doesn't necessarily mean it should be. Society doesn't need an institution that makes it hard for people to be virtuous" (Wishloff, 1993). External stakeholders such as customers, suppliers, and the broader community and ecology play a crucial role in promoting participation within a company. The philosopher Jean-Jacques Rousseau once argued that individuals in society enter into a social contract, giving up some of their personal freedoms in exchange for the benefits of communal living. This principle also extends to companies, where both the external and internal stakeholders collectively form a *communio personarum* with shared interests and responsibilities.

External stakeholders, including customers, suppliers, and the broader community, are essential contributors to this social contract. They ensure that firms are held responsible for their ethical practices, equitable treatment of employees, and commitment to environmental stewardship. Their participation, manifested through purchasing choices and commercial collaborations, has a direct impact on a company's dedication to ethical behavior. Thus, endorsing ethical companies, external stakeholders actively encouraged the cultivation of a responsible and inclusive corporate atmosphere.

This versatile involvement centers on proactive participation, cooperation, and endorsement of a company's goals and endeavors. Firstly, suppliers play a crucial role in the functioning of many firms, and their impact on a company's performance is significant. The dependability and punctual provision of goods and services by suppliers develop a solid foundation of trust and favorable partnerships. Reliable suppliers who regularly produce top-notch items and adhere to agreed-upon delivery schedules enable a firm to operate with greater efficiency and effectiveness. The dependability of a system or process enables a solid basis for cooperation. Additionally, suppliers might act as a source of innovation. They possess extensive knowledge of a company's supply chain and can readily discover opportunities for enhancement and cost reduction. By valuing and implementing supplier proposals, a company not only promotes creativity but also shows a dedication to a mutually advantageous partnership, thereby encouraging greater supplier involvement.

On the other hand, customers, who are the ultimate consumers of a company's products and services, play a crucial role in determining the success of the firm through their comments and input. Interacting with customers to actively seek their comments and ideas is not only a prudent business strategy but also a way to guarantee that a company's products and services are in line with customer requirements and expectations. Companies cultivate client loyalty and advocacy by customizing products and services to fulfill these requirements, which are highly valuable assets in today's fiercely competitive market. Certain pioneering companies take it a step further by engaging customers in the collaborative production of products or services. This cooperative methodology may encompass surveys, focus groups, or brainstorming sessions, wherein customers actively participate in influencing the company's decisions. Such a high degree of engagement not only showcases a dedication to prioritizing the needs of customers, but also fosters a feeling of responsibility among customers, resulting in higher levels of involvement and endorsement of the brand.

In addition to direct consumers and suppliers, the wider community plays a substantial part in the ecosystem of a company. Demonstrating a dedication to creating a beneficial influence beyond financial gains, engaging with the community is achieved through Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programmes, charity, and ecologically friendly practices. This not only promotes community backing but also strengthens brand allegiance, as customers are increasingly inclined towards socially conscientious enterprises. Transparency is a crucial component in fostering community engagement. Transparency regarding business operations, objectives, and principles fosters confidence and enhances credibility among the community. Transparency is particularly crucial in businesses where a company's activities have a substantial local or environmental influence. If a corporation is perceived by the community as transparent and accountable, there is a higher likelihood of active participation and support for its initiatives.

External stakeholders, like contented consumers and devoted suppliers, have the potential to be influential advocates for a company. Content customers frequently recommend the business to others, serving as unofficial advocates for the brand. Suppliers who have a favorable relationship with a firm are more likely to support and advertise its products or services. Moreover, the backing of the community through local collaborations or endorsements can greatly enhance a company's standing and foster engagement. When the community shares the same values and objectives as a firm, their active support can result in heightened brand exposure and confidence.

Also, external stakeholders can serve as vigilant monitors, aiding a company in detecting possible hazards, such as vulnerabilities in the supply chain or challenges to its reputation. By engaging these stakeholders in the process of evaluating and controlling risks, a company can enhance its ability to predict and handle difficulties, thereby protecting its interests and ensuring ongoing involvement in its business operations. Moreover, adherence to laws and regulations is vital for the prosperity of a company. External stakeholders, especially those in the community, may have a significant interest in ensuring that the corporation adheres to legal and ethical standards. Their proactive engagement in maintaining compliance standards enhances the company's overall reputation and trustworthiness.

The involvement of external stakeholders in fostering participation is firmly grounded in philosophical concepts. Their relevance becomes evident when viewed through the perspectives of deliberative democracy, the social compact, and ethical imperatives. These stakeholders, such as civil society organizations, activists, and international entities, serve as intermediates,

representatives, and advocates. They promote and enable citizen engagement by ensuring that individuals have the opportunity to voice their opinions in choices that impact their lives, while also preserving the principles of fairness and unity. In a complex and diverse world, external stakeholders play a crucial role in establishing a society where participation is not only a right but a tangible reality. This allows individuals to actively contribute to defining their own futures, while ensuring that the social compact remains fair and genuine. Their conceptual foundations and practices emphasize the essentiality of their position in the continuous pursuit of democratic engagement.

There are numerous companies who proactively interact with external stakeholders to promote their involvement and cooperation. By seeking advice and feedback from customers, suppliers, communities, and other external groups, they aim to make well-informed decisions and cultivate stronger partnerships. Some of the sample companies that follow this culture are: (1) Starbucks, Starbucks frequently solicits feedback from customers through surveys, suggestion boxes, and its "My Starbucks Idea" platform, which allows people to propose new items and enhancements. Another company that we can cite as an example is GE. GE or General Electric engages in collaborative partnerships with external stakeholders, including as customers and experts, to enhance and advance technology pertaining to renewable energy, healthcare, and aviation. Also, Nestle is doing the same thing by actively collaborating with external partners to address multiple sustainability objectives, including responsible sourcing, water stewardship, and the mitigation of plastic waste.

These instances demonstrate the active involvement of corporations from many sectors in engaging with external stakeholders, such as customers, advocacy groups, suppliers, and local communities. They acknowledge the significance of incorporating external stakeholder feedback to shape their business processes, products, and sustainability activities. Engaging in such interactions can result in more well-informed choices, stronger offerings, and strengthened business commitment to social responsibility.

I. VI. Bridging the gap between internal and external stakeholders

Aligning the interest of internal and external stakeholders can be complex but beside that it is a very crucial task for organization. It is true that coordinating the interests of internal and external stakeholders is a difficult but crucial task for any organization. Long-term success and reputation of the organization depend heavily on maintaining harmonious relationships with all stakeholders, both inside and outside the organization.

According to Edward Freeman, stakeholder theory is a foundational concept in the field of business ethics and management. Organizations can use this theory as a framework to recognize, comprehend, and manage their relationships with different stakeholders. Stakeholder Theory promotes a holistic perspective on business, contending that businesses should take into account the interests of all parties involved, not just shareholders or investors. The theory recognizes that conflicting interests are frequently held by stakeholders both internal and external. Finding a middle ground and balancing these interests is a challenge for organizations looking to generate value for all parties involved. Stakeholder theory focuses on communication that is transparent and easy to understand. In order to comprehend the needs, expectations, and concerns of their stakeholders, organizations should actively engage with them. Stronger bonds and trust are created by this communication. Organizations can better understand the concerns, expectations, and motivations of their stakeholders when there is clear communication between them. Through

attentive listening and interactive communication, entities can pinpoint domains of shared fascination and reciprocal advantages. Good communication becomes crucial when disputes or conflicts emerge. It offers a forum for stakeholders to express their worries, allowing organizations to address them and come up with solutions. Building trust through open and honest communication is essential to preserving goodwill among stakeholders. Long-term partnerships and stakeholder engagement depend significantly on trust.

According to Mitchell, Agle and Wood (1997), developed the stakeholder salience framework to help managers to identify and prioritize stakeholders through the assessment of three attributes: power, legitimacy and urgency. This framework is commonly employed in the field of stakeholder management and is essential in assisting organizations in appreciating the significance and applicability of various stakeholders. Power refers to the ability of a stakeholder to affect the choices, actions, or results of an organization. It includes the ability of the stakeholder to influence or exert control over the organization. High-power stakeholders have a big influence on how well an organization performs and runs. Government regulators, major shareholders, and powerful clients are examples of high-power stakeholders. High-power stakeholders must be identified because their issues frequently require quick attention and action. Legitimacy refers to the perceived appropriateness or validity of a stakeholder's claim to be a stakeholder. It concerns whether the organization and the larger community value and recognize the stakeholder's interests as legitimate. High-legitimacy stakeholders are entitled and justified to have an impact on the organization. Their concerns are in line with the goals, principles, or expectations of the community of the organization. Stakeholders with high legitimacy frequently include local communities, consumers, and employees. It is imperative to attend to the concerns of stakeholders with a high degree of legitimacy in order to uphold moral and socially conscious behavior. The term "urgency" describes how quickly a stakeholder's claims must be addressed and how important they are. It evaluates the urgency with which a stakeholder's concerns need to be resolved. Responding to stakeholders who have high levels of urgency requires quick action, as delays could have detrimental effects on the organization. Activist groups, regulators reacting to public concerns, and crisis situations are examples of high-urgency stakeholders. Determining the stakeholders with the highest urgency helps in preventing or minimizing possible crises.

Based on factors like power, legitimacy, and urgency, organizations can classify stakeholders into distinct groups with the help of the Stakeholder Salience Framework. The categories that result could be definitive stakeholders, dominant stakeholders, dangerous stakeholders, and dependent stakeholders. Definitive stakeholders refers to high-power, high-legitimacy, and high-urgency stakeholders. To solve their concerns, they need our immediate attention as well as our sustained efforts. Neglecting their interests can have serious repercussions. For dominant stakeholders, these are stakeholders with a lot of authority and power, but they might not be very urgent. Their concerns must be addressed for long-term sustainability, as their interests coincide with the organization's mission and values. Dangerous stakeholders refers to the stakeholders that may not have a high level of legitimacy, but they do have a lot of power and urgency. They might not have claims that are morally or ethically justified, but they can nevertheless have a big impact on the company. Strategic negotiations are often necessary to deal with them. Dependent stakeholders, These parties may not have a lot of power, but they do have a lot of legitimacy and urgency. Ignoring their concerns can harm an organization's reputation or ethical standing, even though they might not have an impact on the strategic decisions made. The framework for assessing stakeholder salience offers an organized and methodical way to classify and rank stakeholders. It assists organizations in effectively allocating resources and efforts by

concentrating on the most important stakeholders. The framework facilitates positive stakeholder relationships, addresses stakeholder concerns, and improves overall stakeholder management.

It is challenging but crucial for any organization to coordinate the interests of internal and external stakeholders. The methods for accomplishing this alignment ought to be centered on encouraging mutual gain, openness, and cooperation. Based on the theory and framework provided above, these are some methods for coordinating the objectives of internal and external parties. *Communication*: Establish clear lines of communication with all parties involved in the organization, including shareholders, employees, management, and external parties such as customers, suppliers, the government, local communities, and rival businesses. Inform people on a regular basis about the mission, values, objectives, and performance of the organization. Promote constructive criticism and attentive listening to comprehend the worries, hopes, and drives of all parties involved. *Ethical leadership*: Promoting ethical leadership among executives and upper management is important. Show your dedication to moral principles, social accountability, and environmental sustainability. Leading with ethics creates a culture of trust and accountability in the workforce. *Employee Involvement*: Allow staff members to participate in decisions that directly impact them. Promote empowerment, idea sharing, and staff involvement. Acknowledge the importance of staff members as internal stakeholders who can influence the success of the company. *Social and Environmental Responsibility*: Create and carry out programs pertaining to social and environmental responsibility. Demonstrate a dedication to moral and sustainable business practices that benefit the organization's external stakeholders, such as the environment and nearby communities. *Alignment of Incentives*: Match the long-term objectives of the organization with the incentives of both internal and external stakeholders. Make sure that performance metrics and incentive schemes take into account the interests of customers, shareholders, and employees. *Stakeholders engagement*: Actively interact with stakeholders through partnerships, cooperation, and communication. Work toward shared objectives while attempting to comprehend the various interests of internal and external stakeholders. Utilize input from stakeholders to promote ongoing enhancements to operations, services, and product offerings. *Crisis Management and Response*: Create a plan for handling crises that takes into account the worries of internal and external stakeholders. Retain the capacity to act fast and decisively in the face of emergencies or unforeseen difficulties. Put stakeholder interests first when resolving a crisis. *Regulatory Compliance*: Make sure that all industry-related laws and regulations are strictly followed. Gain a thorough understanding of the regulatory landscape and cooperate and communicate openly with authorities and governmental bodies. *Track and Report Progress*: Create key performance indicators (KPIs) to track the alignment of stakeholder interests over time. Report on a regular basis how well the company is doing in fulfilling the demands of its internal and external stakeholders. Utilize performance data to show your dedication to stakeholder satisfaction and to improve your strategies. Organizations can attempt to strike a balance between the interests of their internal and external stakeholders by putting these strategies into practice. The end effect is a peaceful and effective workplace that fosters moral decision-making, mutual respect, and long-term collaborations—all of which enhance the prosperity and standing of the company.

The role of leadership and corporate culture in fostering participation

Effective leaders empower their employees to participate in internal stakeholder holder dynamics by involving them in decision making processes and encouraging them to take ownership of their work. Leaders need to foster open and transparent communication with the organization, ensuring that employees have the information and resources they need to participate effectively. For a company to be called 'inclusive' it has to value input and perspectives from all employees. When employees feel that their voices are heard and their ideas are valued, they are more likely to

be encouraged to exercise participation. Moreover, a culture that promotes collaboration and teamwork enhances internal stakeholder participation, as employees are encouraged to work together to solve problems and make decisions.

Furthermore, in line with the external stakeholder participation, effective leaders engage with external stakeholders like customers, suppliers, and community members. They actively seek feedback and build relationships that encourage participation in decision-making processes. Leadership that emphasizes ethical behavior and corporate social responsibility can attract external stakeholders who want to participate in organizations that align with their values. A culture of transparency in business operations and decision-making can foster trust and later encourage external stakeholders to also be an agent of change for the companies' actions and impact. If community engagement is being emphasized well in a company, culture will surely attract and involve external stakeholders, especially those who care about the company's impact on society.

Effective leadership in the structure of governance is essential for stakeholders participation in shaping corporate policies and decisions. Leaders in governance roles must facilitate discussions and engage with a diverse range of stakeholders. A corporate culture that values stakeholder engagement as a core part of governance practices encourages the inclusion of diverse voices in decision-making processes.

In both the internal and external stakeholder dynamics, leadership and corporate culture set the tone and create an environment that either encourages or discourages participation. Effective leadership and supportive corporate culture can enhance stakeholder participation, which, in turn, can lead to more informed decisions, improved relationships, and better outcomes for the business and its various stakeholders.

Potential challenges and obstacles

While it is obvious that the theory of participation as it relates to stakeholder engagement in business, can offer numerous benefits, there are also several challenges and obstacles that organizations may encounter when attempting to implement it. Firstly, there are people in the organization that are resistant to change. Employees, leaders, and other stakeholders may resist changes in the way decisions are made and the level of participation allowed. People may be comfortable with the status quo and reluctant to embrace a more participative approach. Moreover, building trust among stakeholders is essential for participation to thrive. A lack of trust can hinder open and honest communication and make it difficult for stakeholders to feel confident in sharing their ideas and concerns. It is also evident in many organizations that ineffective communication can be a significant obstacle to participation. Poorly designed communication processes, language barriers, or mismanagement of information can prevent stakeholders from effectively engaging in discussions.

I. VII. Conclusion

According to Karol Wojtyła, the notion of participation underscores the interdependence of individuals within a society. The statement emphasizes that personal satisfaction is attained by actively participating in group endeavors and taking joint accountability for both self and community welfare. We have seen from this paper that effectively aligning the interests of both internal and external stakeholders is a crucial yet difficult undertaking. The Stakeholder Salience Framework facilitates the classification of stakeholders according to criteria such as power, legitimacy, and urgency. Organizations can employ this framework to effectively prioritize their efforts in engaging with stakeholders.

External stakeholders, including consumers, suppliers, governments, local communities, and competitors, have a substantial influence on the operations and ethical and social obligations of firms. They actively participate in a social agreement that surpasses mere commercial aspects and encompasses ethical and spiritual realms. External stakeholders promote responsible and ethical corporate conduct by supporting organizations that demonstrate a dedication to ethical practices, fair treatment of employees, and environmental conservation. Also, suppliers play a crucial role in enhancing a company's operational efficiency and effectiveness by delivering dependable goods and services. On the other hand, consumers' input and collaboration are vital for tailoring products and services to match their specific requirements. Participating in Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programs and practicing transparent business methods helps to cultivate community backing and brand allegiance. External stakeholders can fulfill the role of advocates, overseeing potential dangers, guaranteeing adherence to legal requirements, and bolstering a company's reputation.

The engagement of external stakeholders in fostering participation is consistent with philosophical principles such as deliberative democracy, the social contract, and ethical obligations. These principles underscore the significance of their contribution to democratic involvement and equitable society outcomes. Starbucks, General Electric (GE), and Nestle are among the firms that actively interact with external stakeholders to obtain feedback and cooperate on sustainability objectives and technological progress. These examples demonstrate the importance of including external stakeholders in determining business choices and fostering corporate social responsibility.

Furthermore, internal stakeholders, such as employees, management, and shareholders, have a vital role in promoting involvement within firms. The notion of participation is in accordance with the theory of collective welfare, which posits that the desires of people within a community, specifically in this context, the organization, should be in agreement with the overarching goals and welfare of the collective.

Internal stakeholders have the responsibility of fostering an atmosphere that promotes engagement by emphasizing common values, inclusiveness, collaboration, and empowerment. Integrity in leadership, establishing moral benchmarks, and serving as a role model are crucial elements in fostering engagement. Many successful organizations, including Google, Zappos, and Costco, commonly engage their internal stakeholders in decision-making processes, actively including their staff in many elements of the organization. Encouraging involvement among employees inside the business not only improves the caliber of decision-making but also reinforces the feeling of collective accountability and dedication to the firm's achievements. The convergence of individual and collective interests is crucial for the enduring prosperity and viability of an organization.

Moreover, organizations face a hard and vital challenge of connecting internal and external stakeholders. The stakeholder theory, which highlights the importance of taking into account the interests of all parties involved, whether they are internal or external, plays a crucial role in managing these interactions. The Stakeholder Salience Framework facilitates the identification and ranking of stakeholders according to their power, legitimacy, and urgency.

In order to align the goals of both internal and external stakeholders, organizations should utilize a range of tactics, such as proficient communication, ethical guidance, employee

engagement, social and environmental accountability, incentive alignment, stakeholder involvement, crisis handling, regulatory adherence, and progress monitoring. By implementing these tactics, it creates an atmosphere that promotes mutual gain, transparency, and cooperation. The role of leadership and business culture is crucial in promoting engagement among both internal and external stakeholders. Competent leaders enable employees to engage by including them in decision-making processes and fostering transparent communication. Participation is enhanced by a culture that places importance on collaboration and teamwork. Leadership in governance positions also fosters dialogues and involvement with a wide range of stakeholders, fostering inclusiveness in corporate decision-making.

To summarize, leadership and corporate culture establish the atmosphere for stakeholder engagement, which can result in well-informed choices, enhanced relationships, and superior outcomes for all stakeholders associated with a firm.

Suggestion for future research directions

This study merely provides a limited glimpse into the profound thinking of the esteemed saint and intellectual, St. Karol Wojtyła. His theory of participation has the ability to establish connections with numerous aspects.

It can serve as a valuable resource for academic research. Indeed, there is a proliferation of contemporary intellectuals who are engaging in the study of his philosophical teachings in application to business practices. . However, as the researcher does his research and studies,

In addition to philosophy, there are numerous more areas that are worthy of study. The individual conducting the research, in order to further investigate the study possibilities pertaining to this paper, academics may contemplate a more complicated examination of "communio personarum" and the notion of participation within the complex dynamics of business stakeholders. This inquiry will specifically examine the complex interaction between employees and employers.

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